

MEASUREMENT LAYER THICKNESS EFFECTS IN MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY AND OTHER FULL-FIELD EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY

In previous research efforts on scarf-repaired composite panels, it was observed that the grating thickness had an amplification effect on interlaminar strains measured using moiré interferometry. This effect is investigated more thoroughly in this research report in the context of the broad scope of full-field experimental techniques.

Keywords: full-field strain, moiré interferometry, edge-effect, interlaminar, laminate

INDRODUCTION

High fidelity modeling of complex materials such as laminated composites, textile composites, and hybrid materials has become feasible as a result of explosive progress in computational capabilities, both with regard to software and hardware. Validation of the results of such analyses remains a challenge. Full-field strain measuring techniques are ideal candidates for examining the complex behavior of these material systems. Many state-of-the-art full-field displacement measurement techniques require or are optimised through the application of a coating layer for measurement purposes. Moiré interferometry requires a diffraction grating on the surface of the specimen which is generally applied as a thin layer of resin with the grating embossed into its surface. Image correlation often requires a thin layer of uniform paint followed by a speckle pattern application. The grid method demands a thin layer of plastic containing the grid to be applied to the measurement region. In each of these cases, the displacement being measured, and hence the strain being calculated, are not the specimen displacements, but the displacements at the surface of the measurement layer. Several past researchers have indicated the importance of considering grating thickness to reduce shear lag and reinforcement effects. Of these, references [1-5] are discussed in more detail subsequently.

Examining the recent work in Ref [6], the author found evidence of interlaminar strain amplification while comparing moiré interferometry measurements of a scarf-bonded composite joint to numerical model results of the joint with and without the grating. These amplifications particularly affected the interlaminar normal strains with no noticeable effect on the interlaminar shear and axial strain distributions. Discrepancies in this component have been documented before at the free-edge of a hole in composites

[7]. These discrepancies were thought to be caused by material property errors within the numerical modeling.

In the present work, a parametric numerical study was conducted on 3D edge effects in quasi-isotropic composite specimens. These specimens were modeled with and without a grating layer. The grating layer thickness and modulus was varied, and strain results were compared with results from the model without a grating. A simplified model to explain the observed grating effects is proposed.

COMMONLY REPORTED GRATING THICKNESS EFFECTS

Grating effects on the measured displacement response have been discussed widely in the literature, although, with a few exceptions, their treatment has generally been superficial. Effects of the grating on measured displacements generally fall into 2 categories; reinforcing effects and shear lag effects. Post [1] mentions a shear lag effect at the strain concentration or strain jump at an interface between dissimilar materials. The strain recorded by the moiré interferometer is a measure of the deformation at the top surface of the grating, not the specimen. Although no numerical or experimental evidence is presented, Post suggests an in-plane region of influence extending approximately one grating thickness away from the concentration before strains consistent with the true specimen behavior are recovered.

The earlier work of Lauer [2] examined the measurement errors on displacements and strains around a hole in isotropic specimens with varying grating thickness and modulus ratio. Experimental and numerical results were obtained on 1.6 mm thick aluminum specimens containing 6.35 mm central holes and a variety of grating thicknesses ranging from 5 μm – 200 μm . The ratio of specimen modulus to grating modulus in these experimental and modeled specimens was approximately 21. Results indicate that, at the hole edge, transverse displacements at the top of the grating surface ranged in error from 0.1%-1.1% with increasing grating thickness, and the axial displacement errors varied from 0.05%-0.26% for the same grating thickness variation. A worst case 3% error was documented in the axial strain at the hole edge for this modulus ratio. A more severe axial displacement error of up to 14% was noted when, in the analyses, the modulus ratio was increased to 60 for the 200- μm thick gratings.

Melin [3] examined the effects of grating thickness in a mechanically loaded [90]₂₄ carbon fiber composite specimen containing an embedded 125- μm optical fiber aligned with the carbon fibers. Moiré interferometry was used to examine the localized strains around the end of the optical fiber, while finite element models, with varying grating thickness and moduli, examined the influence of the grating on the measured strains. The test specimen grating thickness spatially varied from 2-5 μm due to differences in polishing behavior of the constituents. Finite element models consisted of varying the ratio of composite transverse modulus to grating modulus from 1 to 1000 and grating thickness variations from 0-10 μm . The model results clearly show an increasingly large shear lag effect on strain for the modulus ratio of 1000 as grating thickness increases. The sharp variation in displacement across the optical fiber interface is blunted in a region extending approximately 4 times the grating thickness, much farther than suggested by Post [1]. Melin [3] also found that when the modulus ratio was decreased

to 1 there was a slight reinforcing effect on the true strains at the composite surface, but no appreciable reinforcing effects for the modulus ratios of 10 and 1000.

An array of cubic inclusions embedded in a matrix (modulus ratio of 4) was numerically modeled with and without a representative compliant grating layer by Nicoletto and Malfatto [4]. This work was initiated to understand grating thickness effects when moiré interferometry is applied to heterogeneous deformations in polycrystalline materials. It was shown that for a grating thickness to particle spacing ratio of 0.25, the shear lag gradient effect extended about 1.5 times the grating thickness. Also, the peak strains found in the model without a grating were never recovered in the model with the grating. Indeed, as the grating thickness increased, the heterogeneity of the displacement field vanished.

A grating reinforcing effect was documented by Bowman [5] while examining the release of residual stresses in a bi-material system. In this work, a bi-material sample, where one half was epoxy and the other aluminum, was sectioned perpendicular to the bondline between specimen halves. Residual stresses resulting from the elevated cure of the epoxy were then released at the new free-edge for those stress components perpendicular to the new free-edge. The redistribution of strain was recorded using moiré interferometry in which the diffraction grating was replicated onto the specimen at room temperature before sectioning. Note that residual stresses in the grating layer were assumed to be small since they were due only to room temperature cure shrinkage. Corresponding numerical models, with and without modeled grating layers, were conducted. Bowman found clear evidence of reinforcing and shear lag effects from the grating. His experiments and models showed that it was necessary to model the grating to match results closely. However, this was found to be true only on the epoxy side of the specimen where the grating to specimen modulus ratio was approximately 1. Model and experimental results on the aluminum side of the specimen (modulus ratio ~20) showed that results were relatively insensitive to grating thickness.

QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATE PARAMETRIC STUDY

To examine the grating thickness effects of shear lag, reinforcement, and especially amplification, a series of models of a simple quasi-isotropic laminate were constructed and run in a stress analysis code developed at the Air Force Research Laboratory known as the B-Spline Analysis Method (BSAM) [8]. Models of a $[-45_2/0_2/45_2/90_2]_S$ of IM6/3501 carbon fiber laminate were constructed in the BSAM without a grating and with gratings of 50 μm , 25 μm , and 12.5 μm thickness and ratio of composite transverse modulus to grating modulus of approximately 3. In addition, for the 50- μm grating, the modulus ratio was varied between 3, 6, and 12. All models were highly refined, using a single 6th order p-type basis function through each ply of the composite, quadratic spline basis functions in the width and axial directions, and a single 2nd order p-type basis function through the grating thickness. Table 1 describes the nomenclature of each model for identification in subsequent figures. Results will be presented only from the thickest, thinnest, stiffest, and softest grating models in comparison with the model without a grating (those that are in bold text within Table 1).

Table 1: Nomenclature of parametric models (bolded items presented in this report).

Reference Name	Grating Thickness (μm)	Modulus Ratio
Composite	0	NA
G1,E1	50	3
G2,E1	25	3
G3,E1	12.5	3
G1,E2	50	6
G1,E3	50	12

Parametric Modeling Results

Line plots of shear strain (γ_{xz}) and transverse normal strain (ε_{zz}) components while grating modulus is varied are shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. As expected, the shear strain component variation shows significant effects of shear lag through the grating thickness. There appears to be an insignificant effect of grating modulus on this behavior. The effected regions extend approximately twice the grating thickness of $50 \mu\text{m}$. The plot of transverse strain shows that the amplification is present in all plies whether the strain is tensile or compressive. The effect is increased with decreasing modulus.

Figure 1: Comparison of predicted interlaminar shear strain (γ_{xz}) with a variation in modulus ratio ($50\mu\text{m}$ grating thickness) compared with the prediction from the model without a grating.

Figure 2: Comparison of predicted interlaminar transverse strain (ϵ_{zz}) with a variation in modulus ratio ($50\mu\text{m}$ grating thickness) compared with the prediction from the model without a grating.

Figures 3 and 4 examine γ_{xz} and ϵ_{zz} distributions, respectively, as the grating thickness is varied. Not surprisingly, the shear lag effect (Figure 3) is greatly decreased as the grating thickness is reduced. Its region of influence still appears to be twice the grating thickness. The amplification effect, shown in Figure 4 for transverse strain, is generally reduced for the thinner grating, except in regions near ply boundaries. The axial strain component (ϵ_{xx}) was completely unaffected by the presence of the grating.

Figure 3: Comparison of predicted interlaminar shear strain (γ_{xz}) with a variation in grating thickness compared with the prediction from the model without a grating.

Figure 4: Comparison of predicted interlaminar transverse strain (ϵ_{zz}) with a variation in grating thickness compared with the prediction from the model without a grating.

Finally, the variation of the transverse normal strain (ϵ_{zz}) is shown at the composite surface with and without the grating in Figure 5. In this case, the grating is the thickest and stiffest grating modeled in the study. A grating reinforcement effect is apparent across the entire width of the specimen, reducing the strains on the composite. The axial strain component (ϵ_{xx}) was completely unaffected while the shear strain (γ_{xz}) was only slightly altered by the presence of the grating. Ironically, the presence of the grating amplifies the measured ϵ_{zz} while the reinforcing effect decreases the actual ϵ_{zz} at the surface of the composite.

Figure 5: Comparison of predicted interlaminar transverse strain (ϵ_{zz}) between the composite, the composite with the grating, and the grating surface for the composite with the grating.

Proposed Mechanism for Strain Amplification

Of the three interlaminar strains examined (those measurable with moiré) the strain amplification only affects the transverse normal strain component. Examination of the deformed profile of the free-edge of the composite sheds some light on this finding. Figure 6 shows the profile of the free-edge modified only by the U_y component of displacement. In this figure, the deformation has been multiplied by a factor of 20 so that details of the deformation can be visualized. The profile shows a variation of curvatures both concave to the left and concave to the right in various plies.

Figure 6: Plot of the shape of the composite free-edge deformed by the U_y component of displacement. Note that the axial direction (X -direction) is into the paper.

As a thought experiment, imagine a thin layer of epoxy, representing a diffraction grating, attached to a flat, thin, stiff beam, as shown in Figure 7. If the beam is exposed to pure bending, the grating must conform to the curvature imposed upon it by the stiffer material. As this occurs, a strain is induced onto the surface of the epoxy and is thus measured by the interferometer. This mechanism, it is proposed, is analogous to the situation resulting in amplification of the transverse strain in the composite test specimens and the parametric modeling study. That is, the strain due to pure bending induced into the grating (resulting from the curvature of the free-edge due to the variation of U_y) is added to the interlaminar transverse strain of the composite edge created by the 3-D boundary effects present in the quasi-isotropic composite.

Figure 7: Thought experiment of a resin layer on a thin, stiff beam (a) undeformed and (b) deformed in pure bending. The stiffer the beam, the closer the neutral axis of bending is to the left side of the specimen.

To test this proposed mechanism, the U_y profile at the composite surface, predicted from specimen G1,E3 in the study, was used to calculate strains induced by pure bending of a grating/beam combination of the type shown in Figure 7. This was accomplished by calculating the first and second derivatives of the U_y displacement with respect to the Z -coordinate at the composite surface, thus producing the curvature at each point through the composite thickness. These data were then used to calculate the additional strain due to bending using the standard representation of strain due to pure bending as shown in Equation (1), where 't' is the grating thickness. This

$$\epsilon = t \frac{d^2 U_y}{dz^2} / \left(1 + \frac{dU_y}{dz} \right)^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

additional strain was added to the transverse strain component predicted for the composite at the composite surface. A comparison of the original G1,E3 composite strain, the modified strain, and the strain on the grating surface calculated by BSAM are shown in Figure 8. The match between the modified strain, calculated by the addition of curvature induced strains, and the strain calculated through direct modeling of the grating are extremely close. This comparison helps demonstrate the veracity of the proposed strain amplification mechanism.

Figure 8: Comparison between the transverse normal strains (ϵ_{zz}) between the composite free-edge, the same strains modified by the curvature amplification, and the strain on the surface of the grating directly calculated by BSAM.

RAMIFICATIONS OF COATING INDUCED STRAIN AMPLIFICATION

The strain amplification effect has broad implications in the field of experimental mechanics, going beyond testing of composite materials. All full-field optical techniques that use a coating (e.g. moiré interferometry, grid method, digital image correlation, etc.) are subject to a false representation of certain strain components. These components are the ones affected by load induced surface curvature of the specimen. For free-edge effects in composites, this is the interlaminar normal strain. Past work by the author has shown this component to be significantly under predicted by modeling efforts [7], consistent with the observations made herein. Nicoletto [4] uses moiré to measure the behavior of polycrystalline aluminum where there is significant out-of-plane curvature of the gratings at crystal boundaries. The test specimen in Melin [3] may have these effects as well. In many situations, a numerical model of the exact test specimen, as presented here and in [3], is not possible as in the polycrystalline metal of [4]. It is therefore critical, as mentioned in [3, 4, 5 and others], to keep the diffraction grating (or coating) extremely thin, regardless of the dimension of the features on the specimen.

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